

FREQUENCY OF RESTLESS LEGS SYNDROME IN PATIENTS DIAGNOSED WITH FIBROMYALGIA SYNDROME AND THE EFFECTS OF ANTIDEPRESSANT TREATMENT ON RESTLESS LEGS SYNDROME AND SLEEP QUALITY

Keywords

Fibromyalgia,

Restless Legs Syndrome,

Antidepressant

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ABSTRACT

We aim to investigate the frequency of RLS and sleep disturbance in patients diagnosed with FMS, as well as the effects of FMS treatment on sleep quality and Restless Legs Syndrome. This study was conducted on 102 patients diagnosed with Fibromyalgia Syndrome (FMS). Physical examinations of the patients were performed, and the following validated and reliable tools were administered to determine pain intensity, the presence of Restless Legs Syndrome (RLS), sleep quality, and the severity of RLS the Visual Analog Scale (VAS), RLS diagnostic criteria, the RLS Severity Scale, and the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), respectively. Subsequently, patients were started on amitriptyline treatment at a dose of 25 mg/day for Fibromyalgia Syndrome. Patients were recalled for a follow-up after 3 months, and their complaints were re-evaluated. A statistically significant decrease was observed in the post-treatment VAS scores of FMS patients, both with and without a diagnosis of RLS ($p < 0.001$). A statistically significant reduction was also identified in the RLSSS (Restless Legs Syndrome Severity Scale) scores of FMS patients following treatment ($p < 0.001$). Furthermore, a statistically significant decline was noted in the post-treatment PSQI scores of the patients ($p < 0.001$). When examining the mean PSQI values in groups with and without RLS, post-treatment values were found to be significantly lower compared to pre-treatment levels; however, the mean PSQI scores in patients with an RLS diagnosis were significantly higher than those in the group without RLS ($p < 0.001$). Considering that amitriptyline treatment at a dose of 25 mg/day resulted in a significant improvement in patients' complaints and sleep quality at the end of the three-month period, it is suggested that long-term treatment combined with a weight control program aimed at normalizing BMI would lead to further improvements in patients symptoms and sleep quality

INTRODUCTION

Fibromyalgia Syndrome (FMS) is a multisystemic disease characterized by chronic and widespread pain in the musculoskeletal system¹.

In addition to widespread pain, problems such as fatigue, sleep disturbances, distractibility, depressive mood, and cognitive dysfunction occurring in patients with FMS negatively impact their quality of life².

According to the ACR diagnostic criteria defined in 1990, a diagnosis of FMS requires the presence of widespread pain felt in the four quadrants of the body (including the axial skeleton) persisting for at least three months, and the detection of pain upon palpation in at least 11 of the 18 tender points during a physical examination (Figure 1).

Sleep disturbance complaints and RLS are quite common in patients diagnosed with FMS. At the same time, besides the symptoms of fibromyalgia syndrome, these two clinical conditions can be considered among the most important reasons that reduce the patient's quality of life and impair functionality^{3,4,5}.

Since Restless Legs Syndrome (RLS) is a treatable cause of insomnia and sleep disturbance, it has been stated that treating RLS when it accompanies Fibromyalgia Syndrome (FMS) will improve the patients' quality of life^{6,7,8}. In our study, we aim to investigate the frequency of RLS and sleep disturbance in patients diagnosed with FMS, as well as the effects of FMS treatment on sleep quality and Restless Legs Syndrome.

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Figure-1: FMS Tender Points

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted by the Department of Family Medicine at GATA on 102 patients diagnosed with Fibromyalgia Syndrome who applied to the Department of Medical Ecology and Hydroclimatology outpatient clinic. Following the physical examinations, the Visual Analog Scale (VAS), RLS diagnostic criteria, RLS Severity Scale (RLSSS), and Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI)—all of which have proven validity and reliability—were applied respectively to determine the severity of pain, presence of RLS diagnosis, sleep quality, and the severity of restless legs syndrome.

Subsequently, patients were started on amitriptyline treatment at a dose of 25 mg/day for Fibromyalgia Syndrome, and the complaints of the patients called for a follow-up after 3 months were re-evaluated. The data obtained were evaluated

using the SPSS for Windows 15 (Statistical Package for Social Sciences for Windows) software package. For descriptive characteristics and disease-related data, number and percentage were used for categorical data, and mean, standard deviation, median, minimum, and maximum values were used for numerical data.

The conformity of continuous variables to normal distribution was evaluated with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. In the comparison of two groups, the Student's T-Test was used for variables conforming to normal distribution, and the Mann-Whitney U Test was used for those not conforming to normal distribution. Pearson's Chi-Square test or Fisher's Exact test was used for the comparison of discrete variables. The dependent groups T-test was used for intra-group pairwise measurement comparisons. The McNemar test was utilized for the intra-group comparison of discrete variables. The statistical significance level was accepted as $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

All 102 patients included in the study were female, with a mean age of 54.16 ± 12.2 years and a mean BMI of 26.9 ± 4.15 kg/m². It was determined that 76 (74.5%) patients were married and 26 (25.5%) were single. Regarding the educational background, 38 (37.3%) participants were primary school, 11 (10.8%) middle school, 31 (30.4%) high school, and 22 (21.6%) university graduates.

When habits were questioned, it was found that 1 (1%) person used alcohol, 22 (21.6%) smoked, and 26 (25.5%) exercised regularly. It was identified that 60 (58.8%) participants had at least one chronic disease diagnosis and were receiving medical treatment for these diseases. Looking at the chronic diseases, hypertension was present in 28 (27.4%) patients, hypothyroidism in 25 (24.5%), type 2 diabetes in 16 (15.6%), gastroesophageal reflux disease in 11 (10.7%), osteoporosis in 7 (6.8%), coronary artery disease in 6 (5.8%), dyslipidemia in 5 (4.9%), bronchial asthma in 3 (2.9%), congestive heart failure and mitral regurgitation in 2 (1.9%) each, while iron deficiency anemia, vertigo, sleep apnea, and glaucoma were present in 1 (0.9%) patient each.

The average Visual Analog Scale (VAS) scores, average RLS Severity Scale scores (RLSSS), and average Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) results to determine the pain intensity before and after treatment are shown in Table 1. The average pre-treatment VAS score of all patients was calculated as 6.79 ± 1.56 , while the post-treatment average VAS score was 5.26 ± 1.72 . A statistically significant decrease was found in VAS values after treatment ($p < 0.001$).

In the group diagnosed with RLS, the average pre-treatment VAS score was 6.90 ± 1.60 , while the post-treatment VAS score was 5.57 ± 1.67 ($p < 0.001$). In the group without RLS, the pre-treatment VAS score was 6.71 ± 1.54 , while the post-treatment score was 5.03 ± 1.73 . A statistically significant decrease was observed in post-treatment VAS scores for both FMS patients with and without RLS ($p < 0.001$).

A statistically significant decrease was found in the RLSSS scores of FMS patients after treatment ($p < 0.001$). Looking at the pre-treatment PSQI scores of all patients, the total PSQI score of 20 (19.61%) patients was below 5, indicating good

sleep quality, while 82 (80.39%) patients had scores of 5 or above, interpreted as poor sleep quality. Post-treatment PSQI scores were 5 or above in 51 (50%) patients (poor sleep quality) and below 5 in the remaining 51 (50%) patients (good sleep quality). A statistically significant decrease was observed in patients' post-treatment PSQI scores ($p < 0.001$).

Regarding post-treatment PSQI values in the RLS group, 27 (62.8%) patients had poor sleep quality and 16 (37.2%) had good sleep quality. In the group without RLS, 24 (40.7%) patients had poor sleep quality and 35 (59.3%) had good sleep quality. Patients in the group without RLS benefited significantly more from the treatment ($p = 0.027$).

When comparing the average PSQI values of the groups with and without RLS, it was found that post-treatment values were statistically significantly lower than pre-treatment values, and the average PSQI scores in patients with RLS were higher than those in the group without RLS ($p < 0.001$).

DISCUSSION

Fibromyalgia Syndrome (FMS) is a disease characterized by chronic and widespread musculoskeletal pain. In addition to widespread pain, problems such as fatigue, sleep disturbance, distractibility, depressive mood, and cognitive dysfunction occurring in FMS patients impair the individual's ability to cope with life and communicate with their environment⁹.

Although different rates have been detected in studies aimed at determining the prevalence of FMS, it is reported that the prevalence in the general population ranges between 0.5% and 5.8%^{10,11,12}. The risk factors definitively proven in FMS are female gender and advanced age (11). In a study conducted by Wolfe et al. on 8,186 patients diagnosed with FMS, the mean age was determined to be 50.5 ± 12.4 years. All 102 patients participating in our study were female, and the mean age was 54.16 ± 12.2 years.

In a study by Wolfe et al., the average BMI value in patients diagnosed with FMS was found to be above normal at 30.1 ± 7.6 kg/m². We determined the average BMI of the 102 patients in our study to be 26.9 ± 4.15 kg/m². In the group diagnosed with Restless Legs Syndrome (RLS), 18 (41.9%) of the 43 patients were overweight, 14 (32.6%) were

Class I obese, and 2 (4.7%) were Class II obese. BMI values decreased to an average of 5.26 \pm 1.72, representing were found to be statistically significantly higher in the group statistical significance ($p < 0.001$). with RLS compared to the group without RLS ($p < 0.001$).

In a study by Sivas et al. On 80 patients diagnosed with FMS, 18 (22.5%) patients were found to smoke, and none used alcohol¹². Of the 102 patients included in our study, 22 (21.6%) were smokers, and 1 (0.9%) patient used alcohol regularly. The sociodemographic data identified in our study were found to be compatible with literature results.

The primary clinical symptom in FMS is long-term widespread muscle pain. In our study, we investigated VAS scores to determine the pain levels of patients before and after treatment. While the average pre-treatment VAS score for all 102 patients was 6.79 \pm 1.56, the post-treatment VAS scores

In patients diagnosed with FMS, clinical pictures such as sleep disorders and restless legs syndrome frequently coexist alongside psychiatric conditions like major depressive disorder, anxiety disorder, panic disorder, somatization disorder, and post-traumatic stress disorder^{13,14}. Our study has shown that using scales with proven validity and reliability to examine pain levels, sleep quality, comorbid conditions, and their response to treatment will be beneficial in patient follow-up. Furthermore, considering that a clinical condition such as RLS, which disrupts patient comfort, frequently accompanies FMS, it demonstrated that RLS must be taken into account in the evaluation of FMS and patients should be screened for RLS.

Table 1: VAS, RLSSS, PSQI SCORES

	With RLS Diagnosis	Without RLS Diagnosis	p
VAS before treatment	6,90 \pm 1,60	6,71 \pm 1,54	<0,001
VAS after treatment	5,57 \pm 1,67	5,03 \pm 1,73	
RLSSS before treatment	26,72 \pm 6,41	-	<0,001
RLSSS after treatment	19,40 \pm 7,39	-	
PSQI before treatment	9,48 \pm 4,20	6,79 \pm 3,32	<0,001
PSQI after treatment	6,81 \pm 3,67	4,47 \pm 2,50	

Figure-2: Pre- and post-treatment VAS scores in all patients

CONCLUSION

All 102 patients included in the study were female. The mean age of our patients was 54.16 ± 12.2 years. We found no statistically significant difference in mean age between the groups with and without RLS.

RLS accompanied FMS in 43 (42.2%) of our 102 FMS patients. We found a statistically significant higher presence of chronic diseases in the RLS group. BMI values were also found to be statistically significantly higher in the patient group diagnosed with RLS.

When comparing pre-treatment and post-treatment VAS scores, we found a statistically significant decrease. In the RLS group, we identified a statistically significant decrease in RLSSS scores after treatment compared to before treatment. We also determined that PSQI scores after treatment were statistically significantly lower than pre-treatment scores.

It should not be forgotten that RLS may frequently accompany the clinical picture in patients presenting with widespread body pain and diagnosed with FMS. Considering that 25 mg/day amitriptyline treatment significantly improved patient complaints and sleep quality at the end of 3 months, it is believed that long-term treatment and a weight control program to bring BMI to normal values will lead to further improvement in symptoms and sleep quality.

Conflicts of Interest Statement

There are no potential conflicts of interest.

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No

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